

IMPLEMENTING CASE STUDIES TO DEVELOP THE SOCIOLINGUISTIC COMPETENCE OF FUTURE JOURNALISTS

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Annotation. The concept of communicative competence is seen as a complicated polymorphic concept that integrates a variety of competencies in the context of an intercultural approach to teaching foreign languages. One of the most crucial skills for future journalists is sociolinguistic competency. Sociolinguistic competence refers to the capacity to interact with people at their level of development and be aware of non-traditional elements like the culture, way of life, accepted social norms, history, and other social contexts of the speakers of the language with which they interact, plays a role in ensuring successful communication. The focus of the article is to help aspiring English instructors hone their sociolinguistic skills through case studies. Additionally, different case study types, their elements, and the circumstances surrounding language acquisition adaption are taken into account.

Keywords: A case study, a speech exercise, the development of sociolinguistic competency, a future journalist, the analysis of a communication situation, a casual relationship, the correction of errors, and information searching.

Introduction. The concept of communicative competence is seen as a complicated polymorphic concept that integrates a variety of competencies in the context of an intercultural approach to teaching foreign languages. For aspiring English instructors, sociolinguistic competency is one of the most crucial qualities¹. The ability to organize one's speech behavior appropriately for communication situations while taking into account the communicative goal, intention, social statuses, roles of communicants, and the communication environment following the sociolinguistic norm and the attitudes of a specific national linguocultural community is known as sociolinguistic competence. Case studies are the most effective student-centered teaching strategy when it comes to developing the sociolinguistic competencies of

¹ Bobrikova O.S, Ivanova V.I. (2016), Sociolinguistic competence in the professional activity of journalists // Yaroslav ped. Bulletin. № 3.155-159.

future journalists. They can serve as a rich foundation for the development of students' intercultural and sociolinguistic competencies, critical thinking, problem-solving, communication, and other life skills².

The word "case study" refers to a broad range of issues that are presented for consideration and on which students must decide how they would react to challenging scenarios. Because of their multidisciplinary nature, case studies "allow the application of theoretical concepts...bridging the gap between theory and practice." Working on cases encourages students to gather information from many sources and evaluate it. It also helps journalists gauge students' capacity to synthesize, evaluate, and apply information by putting them in situations where they must make challenging judgment calls regarding cultural quandaries. Case studies improve journalists' ability to collaborate and work in a team while also improving their writing and oral communication skills. To teach management skills like "holding a meeting, negotiating a contract, giving a presentation, etc.," case studies "force students into real-life situations³." Situational analysis is frequently employed in classroom instruction. This technique combines the quantitative and qualitative study of the Western predicament. The researcher can use situational analysis to reduce the number of case studies they need to include in their study. It is sufficient for him to choose one and think about it from all angles. Case Study proves to be the most practical and trustworthy strategy for a variety of study issues.

The creation of tasks and hypotheses typically comes before data gathering in exploratory research. These kinds of particular circumstances are viewed as a form of pre-research. Explanatory case studies are useful for determining the causes of a certain circumstance because they allow us to apply the approach of acting following the model in situations that are extremely complicated and multivariate. To prepare for potential issues that can develop when investigating Case Studies, the researcher must start the study of events with a theoretical description. The study methodology was used when conducting research Case Studies, which also integrate descriptive and explanatory elements, concerning the development of the sociolinguistic ability of future journalists

² Leaver B.L., Ehrman M., Shekhtman B. Achieving success in second language acquisition // Cambridge University Press, 2005.p.265.

³ Muhamadjonovna, S. D. (2020). The development of sociolinguistic competence of future journalists through computer technologies. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 8 (3) Part II, 147-150.

in independent education. The journalist must guide the students toward understanding that there is a problem and that a solution is necessary, which necessitates a problem condition⁴.

With active speech interaction between students and journalists as equal speech partners, it can discuss the problem situation, formulate the problem, look for solutions to it, and ultimately solve the problem. The journalist assists students at all stages of working with educational materials, provides for a variety of educational and other problems and solutions, educates students on the purpose of the actions they take and the range of their mental operations, and encourages learners to be conscious of their actions through reflection. The key component of the research technique, as opposed to the problem presentation approach, is that the journalist creates and provides students with problem communication and research-related cognitive activities⁵. The proposed problem is recognized and examined by journalists, who then create approaches to its resolution and make their case for the choice. Case Studies, which are thought of as speech exercises, are made concrete by the tasks of assessing the sociolinguistic circumstances of a communicative situation, identifying cause-and-effect correlations, and establishing and correcting faults that inhibit the selection of the appropriate register in communication. The key point is that the mechanisms of creative thinking are engaged and students gain research experience.

Journalists can find fundamentally new material or investigate what is already known while working on these projects. When performing creative tasks, there is a certain value in comparing the phenomena being studied in the native and studied cultures, studying the difficulties of intercultural communication, and introducing oneself to a different national-linguistic cultural community by using someone else's speech experience based on the sociolinguistic knowledge, skills, and abilities that have been acquired. We suggested using the Case Study as a technique that implements the principle of problematic at the stage of developing the sociolinguistic competence of aspiring journalists within the scope of the research methodology. In didactics, the case study is viewed as a teaching strategy based on the examination of real-world events,

⁴ Muhamadjonovna, S. D. (2020). The key concepts of forming sociolinguistic competence of future journalists. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR)*, 9(5), 118-121. Doi: 10.5958/2278-4853.2020.00157.3.

⁵ Passov E.I. (1985), *The communicative method of teaching foreign language speaking: a guide for journalists of foreign languages*. lang.// - M.: Education, 1985 p.208.

which has evolved into one of the key technologies of business education (or, in one interpretation, the study of particular scenarios). There are other types of methods used in foreign publications that fall within the journalism umbrella, including case studies and the case method⁶.

A technique for teaching decision-making that uses the analysis of a particular circumstance obtained from practical activities is known as the case study method. The criteria for content selection were chosen based on the preferences, requirements, and linguistic level of the journalists. The social multimedia literary circle's interactive element and algorithm presumptively go through the following stages:

- 1) Independent reading of the case studies that have been shared, where journalists are urged to use critical thinking to solve the issues and collaborate on case discussions/arguments once a week on the platform;
- 2) Journalists should compile their dictionary of new words, expressions, and case study sociolinguistic phenomena that will be used to summarize what has been read, debated, and resolved.
- 3) Active participation in the platform's collaborative case study discussions.
- 4) Creating their case studies that can be utilized for further group discussions and writing comments on the case studies they have read and watched in videos.

Additionally, the methods and forms of control of journalists' independent education were controlled on the platform as part of the technology's control and diagnostic component⁷.

Conclusion. The use of Case Studies ensures the presence of a strategy and tactics for communicators, actualizes the relationships of communication participants, determines the productivity of statements, and contributes to the development of speech activity and independence at the stage of the development of sociolinguistic competence of future journalists in controlled independent education.

REFERENCES:

⁶ Riskulova K.D. (2018) Didactic conditions for the formation of sociolinguistic competence of future journalists of a foreign language // Bulletin of Science and Education. (4).40.

⁷ Davis, C. & Wilcock, E. Teaching materials using case studies. UK Centre for Materials Education, Higher Education Academy. <http://www.materials.ac.uk/guides/casestudies.asp>.

1. Bobrikova O.S, Ivanova V.I. (2016), Sociolinguistic competence in the professional activity of journalists // Yaroslav ped. Bulletin. № 3.155-159.
2. Daly, P. (2002). Methodology for using case studies in the business English language classroom. Internet TESL Journal. 8(11). <http://Daly, 2002/Techniques/Daly CaseStudies/>
3. Davis, C. & Wilcock, E. Teaching materials using case studies. UK Centre for Materials Education, Higher Education Academy. <http://www.materials.ac.uk/guides/casestudies.asp>.
4. Leaver B.L., Ehrman M., Shekhtman B. Achieving success in second language acquisition // Cambridge University Press, 2005.p.265.
5. Levina, M.M. (2001) “Technologies of professional pedagogical education”. Moscow: Academy, p.272.
6. Mamura Alimova, (2018) Cultural Bridges, Course book on intercultural competence // Namangan 2018, p.14-16.
7. Muhamadjonovna, S. D. (2020). A Set of Methodological Tools for the Formation of Sociolinguistic Competence of Future English Teachers. The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations, 2(12), 298-302.
8. Muhamadjonovna, S. D. (2020). The development of sociolinguistic competence of future journalists through computer technologies. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences, 8 (3) Part II, 147-150.
9. Muhamadjonovna, S. D. (2020). The key concepts of forming sociolinguistic competence of future journalists. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR), 9(5), 118-121. Doi: 10.5958/2278-4853.2020.00157.3.
10. O'ktamova N. “The main principles of teaching sociolinguistic competence for adult learners”. ЎЗМУ ХАБАРЛАРИ, ВЕСТНИК нууз, АСТА нууз Мирзо Улуғбек Номидаги Ўзбекистон Миллий Университети илмий журнали, 2022. 197 p.;
11. O'ktamova N., “The main principles of teaching sociolinguistic competence for adult learners”, О‘ЗБЕКИСТОН МИЛЛИЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТИ ХАВАРЛАРИ, 2022, [1/5/1] ISSN 2181-7324. 2022. 197-199 p.;
12. Passov E.I. (1985), The communicative method of teaching foreign language speaking: a guide for journalists of foreign languages. lang.// - М .: Education, 1985 p.208.

ISSN (E): 2181-4570

13. Polat E.S., Bukharkina M.Yu, (2007) Modern pedagogical and information technologies in the education system: textbook. manual for stud. higher. study. //Moscow: Academy, p.368.

14. Riskulova K.D. (2018) Didactic conditions for the formation of sociolinguistic competence of future journalists of a foreign language // Bulletin of Science and Education. (4).40.

15. Riskulova, K.D (2017) DSc dissertation “System of formation of sociolinguistic competence of future journalists”, Tashkent, 179.

16. The Common European Framework of Reference for Languages. URL: http://www.coe.int/T/DG4/Portfolio/documents/Framework_EN.pdf (date accessed: 05.02.2021).

17. Uktamova N., Teshabayeva D., “Competence-based approaches to teaching English as a foreign language to the students in journalism”, Modern education & research institute (Belgiya), xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari, medialogvistika rivojlanishining zamonaviy tendensiyalari, 2022. 373-378 p.;

